

Association between rainfall and *Escherichia coli* in live bivalve molluscs harvested in Sardinia, Italy

A.G. Mudadu^a, C. Spanu^{b,*}, S. Salza^a, G. Piras^a, M.T. Uda^a, L. Giagnoni^b, G. Fois^c, J.G. Pereira^d, J.C.F. Pantoja^d, S. Virgilio^a, T. Tedde^a

^a Veterinary Public Health Institute of Sardinia, Complex Structure of Food Hygiene, Via Duca degli Abruzzi 8, Sassari 07100, Italy

^b Department of Veterinary Medicine, University of Sassari, Via Vienna 2, 07100 Sassari, Italy

^c Meteorological, Agrometeorological and Ecosystem Service of the Regional Environment Protection Agency of Sardinia (ARPAS), Viale Porto Torres 119, 07100 Sassari, Italy

^d Department of Animal Production and Preventive Veterinary Medicine, São Paulo State University (UNESP), Rua Prof. Walter Mauricio Correia SN, Rubião Jr., Botucatu, SP 18618-681, Brazil

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ABSTRACT

Rainfall is generally accepted as one of the most important factors associated with an increased level of *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs. Performing microbiological risk assessment is relevant to official control authorities to determine the sanitary status of harvesting areas and, therefore, develop monitoring strategies and identify management practices that could be used to improve the quality and safety of the final product. The present study aimed to investigate the impact of rainfall on the content of *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs farmed in Sardinia (Italy). Enumeration of *E. coli* was performed according to the Most Probable Number (MPN) method (ISO 16649-3) on 1,920 bivalve samples collected from 7 regional counties between 2018 and 2020. Bivalve molluscs samples included 955 mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), 500 oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*), 325 clams (*Ruditapes decussatus*), 94 warty venus (*Venus verrucosa*), and 46 lagoon cockles (*Cerastoderma glaucum*). Rainfall data were obtained by the Department of Meteorology of the ARPA Sardegna. For each sampling site, GPS coordinates were used to identify gauge stations within catchment areas. Cumulative rain (mm) was recorded 1, 3, 5, 7, and 15 days before sampling, among which the 7-day cumulative rain was the strongest predictor of *E. coli* counts. Several thresholds of 7-day cumulative rain (from <10 mm up to >300 mm) before sampling were used to estimate the chances of a non-compliant sample (*E. coli* levels above the limit for sanitary class A; 230 MPN/100 g). The 7-day cumulative rain was positively associated with the chances of non-compliance. When the 7-day cumulative rain before sampling was >300 mm, 80.5 % of the samples were non-compliant, and the odds of a non-compliant sample were 23.6 times higher, as compared to samples harvested when the 7-day cumulative rainfall was <10 mm. Precipitation data could be a useful tool for interpreting anomalous results from official control authorities and reduce the costs that originate from closure of production areas.

1. Introduction

Bivalve molluscs farming in Italy is a well-developed sector, ranking third in Europe, after Spain and France. Italy is the world's second largest producer of Japanese carpet shell (*Ruditapes philippinarum*) and the third-largest producer of mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) (Wijsman, Troost, Fang, & Roncarati, 2019). With a coastline of over 1,800 km, the island of Sardinia has a long tradition in shellfish production, with the first mussel farming plant established in 1919 in the Gulf of Olbia (North-East coast) (Laore, 2016). Olbia, together with Oristano (West

coast), is the main location of production where intensive bivalve molluscs farming is generally conducted in brackish lagoons and marine farms. Other important production areas are located in wetlands, such as Tortoli pond (South-East), in the lagoon complex of Sarrabus, Santa Gilla (South), Cirdu (South-West), and Porto Pozzo lagoon (North-East). The regional farms produce mostly mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), which accounts for approximately 80 % of the regional aquaculture sector.

Bivalve mollusc production in Sardinia is seasonal, peaking in spring and summer. During the rest of the year, mussels are mostly imported from other countries, such as Spain and Greece. Sardinia is one of the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: cspanu@uniss.it (C. Spanu).

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Italian regions where oyster production (*Crassostrea gigas*) is carried out with greater success. Almost the entire production is from specialized farms located in the San Teodoro Pond located in the North-East coast. The remaining production is from other farms operating in lagoon environments. In the Alghero area (North-West) business operators have been recently applying for registration of new bivalve mollusc farms. The main production areas of bivalve molluscs along Sardinian coastline are represented in Fig. 1.

Bivalve molluscs are filter feeders and can become contaminated by filtering inorganic matter, viruses, and bacteria from the surrounding water, in addition to selectively filtering phytoplankton and zooplankton (Sferlazzo et al., 2018). Zoonotic pathogens such as

bacteria (e.g. *Salmonella*, *Arcobacter*, *Vibrio*, *Shigella*, pathogenic *E. coli*), viruses (e.g. *Norovirus*, *Hepatitis A virus*) and protozoans (*Giardia duodenalis*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Toxoplasma gondii*) can contaminate shellfish, especially when they are grown in water polluted with human (i.e., sewage) or animal (e.g. livestock, wildlife, and agriculture) feces (Butt, Aldridge, & Sanders, 2004; Campos et al., 2015; Gyawali & Hewitt, 2020; Lorenzoni et al., 2021; Marceddu et al., 2017; Mudadu et al., 2021; Polo, Varela, & Romalde, 2015; Tedde et al., 2019). Foodborne disease resulting from the ingestion of bivalve molluscs contaminated with enteric bacteria present on sewage discharges into the sea, has been reported since the 19th century (Foote, 1895). Perry and Bayliss (1936) were the first authors to propose the use of

Fig. 1. Location of the study showing sampling locations within corresponding county (red frame) and gauge stations within each catchment area (delimited by white lines). Counties: Sassari (1), Olbia-Tempio (2), Nuoro (3), Ogliastra (4), Oristano (5), Carbonia-Iglesias (6), Cagliari (7). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Escherichia coli as an indicator of significant faecal pollution in water, and they also indicated a variation in the degree of correlation due to season and weather conditions. *E. coli* and *Enterococcus* spp. are found in feces of warm-blooded animals, including humans, in high and relatively stable concentrations. The density of *E. coli* in human feces normally varies from 10^6 to 10^7 cells/g (Forsythe, 2020). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2010), one of the main causes of faecal pollution in seawater is untreated wastewater. Paruch, Paruch, Eiken, and Sorheim (2019) found that rural wastewater contains a high microbial diversity, whereas urban wastewater has lower microbial biodiversity, but higher rates of faecal contamination. Although human feces are generally considered a higher risk for contamination, currently there is insufficient evidence to consider animal feces as a lower risk (Pinn, Fernandez, Malham, & Le Vay, 2021).

Despite several routes of contamination having been identified, the main sources and mechanisms of faecal contamination of bivalve molluscs are urban runoff (human sewage), the presence of intensive livestock agriculture, and wastewater treatments (Campos, Kershaw, & Lee, 2013).

The exposure to pathogens (mostly gastro-enteric) accumulated in the mollusc's tissues represents a serious threat to consumer health due to consumption of raw or lightly cooked bivalve molluscs (Butt et al., 2004; Iwamoto, Ayers, Mahon, & Swerdlow, 2010; Lees, 2000; Mudadu et al., 2021; Potasman, Paz, & Odeh, 2002; Savichtcheva & Okabe, 2006). Therefore, microbiological monitoring of fishery waters is essential to ensure the safety of bivalve molluscs. *E. coli* is a reliable indicator of fecal contamination (Baylis, Uyttendaele, Joosten, & Davies, 2011; Jang et al., 2017), that is used in the European Union to assess the microbiological quality of bivalve mollusc and growing water. Within the European Union Member states, the official control regulations applied to live bivalve production sites require that competent authorities classify production and relay areas for live bivalve molluscs (EU Regulation 2017/625) and that producers collect bivalve shellfish for commercial sale only from classified production areas (EC Regulation 853/2004). In addition, the rules for the official controls on products of animal origin including live bivalves, specify that all EU Member States must routinely monitor the level of faecal contamination in production and relaying areas, and classify these production areas accordingly (EC Regulation 2019/627).

Several factors influence the microbial quality of water where bivalve molluscs are produced and harvested. These include environmental factors (e.g. rainfall, solar radiation, temperature, season) and the characteristics of the catchment area (e.g. hydrogeology, topography, river network, water salinity, water depth, wind-driven currents, and tidal cycle) (Campos et al., 2013; Campos, Kershaw, Lee, Morgan, & Hargin, 2011; Coulliette, Money, Serre, & Noble, 2009; Crowther, Kay, & Wyer, 2001; Kelsey, Porter, Scott, Neet, & White, 2004; Lipp et al., 2001; Pinn & Le Vay, 2023). Overall, rainfall events are generally accepted as one of the most important factors associated with an increased level of fecal indicator organisms (FIO) and *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs as they transport contaminants into shellfish-growing areas (Campos & Cachola, 2007; Campos et al., 2011; Derolez, Soudant, Fiandrino, Cesmat, & Serais, 2012; Lee & Morgan, 2003; Martinez-Urtaza et al., 2004).

The minimum amount of rainfall required to produce a significant increase of *E. coli* levels in bivalve molluscs depends on the specific characteristic of the sampling site: catchment size, land use in the watershed, distance of sampling from the coast, and climatic conditions due to seasonal variability (Bougeard et al., 2011; Campos & Cachola, 2007; Campos et al., 2011; Ciccarelli et al., 2017). A significant increase in *E. coli* load has been observed after weak precipitation events following dry periods, whereas higher amounts of precipitation are needed to produce the same increase in fecal coliforms after prolonged wet conditions (Iqbal & Hofstra, 2019; Leonardi, Matsoukis, & Carnacina, 2020). The time elapsed between the rainfall event and the variation in *E. coli* load (i.e., lag-time) showed the highest correlation from

<3 days up to 7 days depending on local environmental conditions and hydrogeological factors (Campos et al., 2011; Coulliette et al., 2009; Kelsey et al., 2004). Previous investigations also suggest differences in *E. coli* concentration among species of bivalve molluscs reared in the same area (Amouroux, & Soudant, 2011; Younger & Reese, 2013).

In the European Union and other countries, such USA and Canada, rainfall variability is considered by official control authorities to determine the sampling strategies for monitoring of growing water and interpretation of anomalous *E. coli* data (CFIA, 2018; EC, 2021; FDA, 2019). The use of rainfall data could be used as a predictor for increased *E. coli* contamination of bivalve molluscs. Therefore, it could be used by official control authorities to interpret anomalous microbiological results, and by businesses, to plan the harvesting time and reduce the risk of exceeding the *E. coli* limit, preserving their ability to trade. To date little information is available on the association between rainfall events and *Escherichia coli* levels in live bivalve molluscs harvested in Sardinia. A deeper knowledge of the effect of precipitations on the microbiological quality of bivalve molluscs farmed in Sardinia will contribute to reduce the risk of contamination of shellfish placed on the market and to ensure the safety of consumers. In addition, it would support official control authorities in the adoption of a risk-based approach while monitoring bivalve molluscs' production and harvesting areas aimed to protect public health.

The general aim of the present study was to provide control authorities and food business operators with simple and accessible evidence-based information to support decision-making after rainfall events. Therefore, the influence of rainfall events on the level of *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs in different production areas of Sardinia was investigated. Specific objectives of the present study were to: a) investigate the association between rainfall events and *E. coli* levels in bivalve molluscs using both cumulative mm of rain and number of rainy days; b) define the time period (lag-time) between a rainfall event and the greatest increase in *E. coli* levels; and c) estimate the odds of a non-compliant sample, as a function of the amount of rainfall prior to harvesting and other explanatory variables studied.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples collection

Edible bivalve molluscs samples were collected between 2018 and 2020 from 25 sampling sites located in 7 counties of Sardinia (Italy), the second largest island in the Mediterranean Sea (40°03'N, 9°05'E). Bivalve samples were collected as part of an official control program that included microbiological analysis for classification and monitoring of production areas. Sardinian production areas were located mainly in brackish lagoons and marine farms along the island coastline. Sampling areas within each regional county, and representative of the regional bivalve mollusc production, are indicated in Fig. 1.

A total of 1,920 bivalve sample units including 955 (49.7 %) mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), 500 (26.0 %) oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*), 325 (16.9 %) clams (*Ruditapes decussatus*), 94 (4.9 %) warty venus (*Venus verrucosa*), and 46 (2.4 %) lagoon cockles (*Cerastoderma glaucum*) were collected. Of these, 180 (3.4 %) originated from class A areas, 1,679 (87.5 %) from class B areas and 61 (3.2 %) from class C areas. Supplementary Table 1 shows the distribution of bivalve molluscs species by counties. Each sample unit was comprised of a minimum number of individual animals, according to ISO 6887-3 (ISO, 2003). After collection, samples were transported refrigerated to the laboratory in sterile plastic bags and examined within 24 h.

2.2. Microbiological analysis

Samples were externally cleaned and aseptically prepared for microbiological analysis according to ISO 6887-3 (ISO, 2003). Enumeration of *E. coli* was conducted using the Most Probable Number

(MPN) reference method ISO 16649-3 (ISO, 2015). Briefly, the MPN is a two-stage, five-tubes three-dilution method. In the first resuscitation step tubes of mineral-modified glutamate medium (MMGB) were inoculated with a series of diluted shellfish homogenates and incubated at 37 ± 1 °C for 24 h. *E. coli* was successively confirmed by subculturing acid-producing tubes onto Tryptone Bile X-GLUC (TBX) Agar (Biolife, Milan, Italy). The MPN was computed based on the number of positive tubes from 5×3 MPN tables (ISO, 2007). The MPN lower detection limit is $<18 E. coli/100$ g.

2.3. Rainfall data

Historical data on total daily rainfall from 2018 to 2020 were obtained by the Department of Meteorology of the ARPA Sardegna. Rainfall was expressed in mm, as the depth of water collected from a rain gauge on a flat surface. The resolution of rain gauges was 0.2 mm. Precipitation records included daily rainfall levels back to 15 days before sampling. For each sampling site, based on GPS coordinates, rainfall data were collected by combining the level of rainfall recorded from all the gauge stations within the same catchment area (up to six rain gauges depending on the extent of the catchment area). Fig. 1 shows the location of gauge the stations within each catchment area.

2.4. Statistical analysis

2.4.1. Descriptive statistics

E. coli MPN/100 g results were used to assign bivalve molluscs to one of the three sanitary classification categories laid down for harvesting areas by Regulation No 2019/627. Categorical variables were created for bivalve mollusc species (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Crassostrea gigas*, *Ruditapes decussatus*, *Venus verrucosa*, or *Cerastoderma glaucum*), year of collection (2018, 2019, or 2020), season (autumn, spring, summer, or winter) and county of origin (1–7). The PROC FREQ of SAS (SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA) was used to produce descriptive statistics.

2.4.2. Rainfall effect on *E. coli*

For each sampling site, total rainfall (mm) was recorded on the sampling day (day 0), and one (–1), three (–3), five (–5), seven (–7), and fifteen (–15) days before sampling. For each time interval, the cumulative mm of rain and the number of rainy days were calculated. A rainy day was defined when there was >1 mm of precipitation.

Since the distribution of cumulative rainfall and number of rainy days at the different intervals (Day 0 to Day-15) were highly skewed, their correlation with the *E. coli* level (log MPN/100 g) was estimated by use of the Spearman's coefficient of correlation (ρ) with PROC CORR (SAS Institute) (Campos et al., 2011).

To assess the association between rainfall and *E. coli* concentration, the 7-day cumulative rain (mm) before sampling (R7cum) was used to create different rainfall categories, as follows: <10 , >10 to 50, >50 to 100, >100 to 150, >150 to 200; >200 to 250, >250 to 300, and >300 mm. A multivariable logistic regression model (PROC LOGISTIC, SAS Institute) was constructed to estimate the odds of a non-compliant sample (*E. coli* values above the limit for sanitary class A; >230 MPN/100 g), as a function of R7cum and other covariates (season, species, and county, as described above). Although the effects of species and county were not statistically significant, they were kept in the final model to produce adjusted R7cum estimates and to control for their confounding effects. The analysis was performed at a significance level of 0.05.

3. Results

3.1. *E. coli* levels in bivalve molluscs

During the three-year period, 640 samples were collected in 2018, 629 in 2019, and 651 in 2020. Of the total 1,920 bivalve molluscs samples analyzed for *E. coli*, 1,556 (81.04 %) were within the

microbiological standards required for class A harvesting areas (≤ 230 MPN/100 g), 302 (15.73 %) were within the limit for class B areas (>230 and $\leq 4,600$ MPN/100 g), and 62 (3.23 %) were within the limit for class C areas ($>4,600$ and $\leq 46,000/100$ g). None of the samples exceeded the limit for prohibited areas ($>46,000$ MPN/100 g). Of the samples within the limit of class A areas, 1,009 (52.55 %) were below the detection limit of the MPN method (<18 MPN/100 g). The distribution of the sanitary classification categories was not different among the mollusc species ($P > 0.05$; Table 1). The sanitary class was associated with year of collection, county of origin, and season ($P < 0.05$; Fig. 2). The *E. coli* level (MPN/100/ g) observed over time in bivalve molluscs reared in Sardinia varied largely during the 3-year observation period, ranging from <18 to 2,400 (median = 18; Fig. 3).

3.2. Correlation of rainfall and *E. coli* level in bivalves

Cumulative mm of rain showed a higher correlation with *E. coli* concentration than the number of rainy days. The correlation between rainfall and *E. coli* was also assessed by mollusc species (Table 2). *Mytilus galloprovincialis* was the mollusc species with the greater correlation coefficient ($\rho = 0.328$) (Table 2). The cumulative amount of rain fallen at each observation interval was significantly associated with year and season. Overall, 2018 was the rainiest year followed by 2020 and 2019, while autumn was the rainiest season. The average mm of rain (\pm SD) is reported in Supplementary Table 2 and Fig. 4.

3.3. Lag-time between rainfall and *E. coli* increase

The correlation coefficient (ρ) between rainfall and the level of *E. coli* in bivalves varied largely depending on the time interval and mollusc species considered. Overall, the highest correlation coefficients were found when sampling was conducted 7 days after the rainfall event, when the cumulative mm of rain was considered ($\rho = 0.240$) (Table 2).

3.4. Increased risk of *E. coli* contamination after rainfall

Results of the multivariable analysis (Table 3) showed that the percentage of non-compliant samples increased significantly as R7cum ranged from <10 mm (15.3 %) to >300 mm (80.5 %). As compared to samples that were harvested when R7cum was <10 mm, the odds of a non-compliant sample increased by 1.5, 6.1, and 23.6 when R7cum was 10–50, 150–200, and >300 mm, respectively (Table 3). The effect of season remained significant in the multivariable model; the percentage of non-compliant samples was significantly higher in autumn (32.1 %; OR = 2.0) and spring (24.0 %; OR = 1.5), as compared to winter (12.4 %; referent category) (Table 3). There was great variation among counties, with the proportion of non-compliant samples ranging from 4.1 % (Carbonia-Iglesias) to 39.3 % (Nuoro) (Table 3).

4. Discussion

While the concentration of *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs varied widely during the observation period, over 80 % of the samples were below the threshold for sanitary class A, indicating an overall good hygienic quality of harvesting areas (median = 18 MPN/100 g). In fact, there was a limited number of samples (3.2 %) within class C. No significant difference was observed in the distribution of sanitary class among bivalve species and year of collection. We observed a lower prevalence of sanitary class A samples in autumn, which was characterized by the greatest amount of rainfall at each of the time intervals considered (Supplementary Table 2). The link between precipitation and increased microbial pollution in rivers, estuarine and marine coastal environments has been reported (Dwight et al., 2011; Pommepuy et al., 2004; Shehane, Harwood, Whitlock, & Rose, 2005). Non-compliance with *E. coli* levels after rainfall events leads local authorities to downgrade or close harvesting areas, limiting the businesses' ability to trade. Economic losses

Table 1

Distribution into sanitary levels based on *Escherichia coli* MPN/100 g results by bivalve molluscs species in samples collected between 2018 and 2020 in 25 farming locations of Sardinia (Italy).

Bivalve molluscs	<detection limit*	Sanitary Class			Total
		A	B	C	
Mussels (<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>)	503 (52.7 %)	802 (83.98 %)	130 (13.61 %)	23 (2.41 %)	955 (49.74 %)
Oyster (<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>)	300 (60.00 %)	391 (78.20 %)	83 (16.60 %)	26 (5.20 %)	500 (26.04 %)
Clams (<i>Ruditapes decussatus</i>)	144 (44.31 %)	250 (76.92 %)	67 (20.62 %)	8 (2.46 %)	325 (16.93 %)
Warty venus (<i>Venus verrucosa</i>)	38 (40.43 %)	78 (82.98 %)	13 (13.83 %)	3 (3.19 %)	94 (4.90 %)
Lagoon cockle (<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>)	24 (52.17 %)	35 (76.09 %)	9 (19.57 %)	2 (4.35 %)	46 (2.40 %)
Total	1,009 (52.55 %)	1,556 (81.04 %)	302 (15.73 %)	62 (3.23 %)	1,920

*: <18 MPN; Class A: ≤230 (column A is cumulative of MPN below the detection limit); Class B: >230 and ≤4,600; Class C: >4,600.

Fig. 2. Number of bivalve molluscs samples falling into one of the three sanitary categories (A, B, and C) based on the *Escherichia coli* level by year of collection, mollusc species, county of origin and season.

to farmers are exacerbated by the difficulties of local authorities to predict such events and to timely assess water quality (Tilburg, Jordan, Carlson, Zeeman, & Yund, 2015). The time required for microbiological testing to assess faecal bacteria make these methods not suitable as an early warning system.

Several studies have been conducted to predict the microbiological quality of harvesting areas using mathematical models that accounted for the effect of interacting environmental factors (De Brauwere et al., 2014; Fiandrino, Martin, Got, Bonnefont, & Troussellier, 2003; Kashefipour, Lin, & Falconer, 2006; Pommepuy et al., 2005). Nonetheless, rainfall is one of the most important factors associated with an increased level of *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs (Campos & Cachola, 2007; Campos et al., 2011; Derolez et al., 2012; Lee & Morgan, 2003; Martinez-Urtaza et al., 2004). To the authors' knowledge, no previous investigation has been conducted to evaluate the impact of precipitation on the concentration of *E. coli* in bivalve molluscs farmed in Sardinia. Francy et al. (2013) suggested that several regression-model approaches can be applied to predict *E. coli* levels, and that selection of the appropriate explanatory variables is catchment or site-specific. They also pointed that rainfall was among the most predictive variables.

Being aware of the limitations of using a simplified model to assess the impact of rainfall on the sanitary status of harvesting areas, the present study aimed to provide an accessible tool to official control authorities and businesses to predict the compliance of *E. coli* levels in bivalve molluscs after rainfall events. As previously discussed, there are

several interacting factors which are not always known or easily accessible or measurable on a daily basis.

After screening for the most useful rainfall variables for predicting *E. coli* non-compliance, R7cum was a stronger predictor than the number of rainy days before sampling, being, therefore, considered for further analyses. On a practical basis, business operators could have access to rainfall data and make better harvest decisions. This finding agrees with previous investigations (Campos et al., 2011; Colaiuda, Di Giacinto, Lombardi, Ippoliti, Giansante, Latini, & Mascilongo, 2021; Derolez et al., 2012; Lipp, Farrah, & Rose, 2001), whereas other studies (Cicarelli et al., 2017; Coulliette et al., 2009; Kelsey et al., 2004) showed a higher impact of rainfall within 2–4 days previous to sampling. Differences in the lag-time may be due to several environmental and hydro-geological factors other than precipitation that may impact fecal contamination (Campos et al., 2011; Coulliette et al., 2009; Kelsey et al., 2004). Among bivalve species, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* showed the higher correlation between rainfall and *E. coli* contamination, followed by *Ruditapes decussatus* and *Venus verrucosa*, whereas lower correlation coefficients were observed for *Cerastoderma glaucum* and *Crassostrea gigas*, suggesting possible differences in the accumulation and clearance mechanisms due to differences in rearing systems and in filter-feeding activity (Amouroux, & Soudant, 2011; Younger & Reese, 2013).

Results of multivariate logistic regression indicated that, regardless of season, county, and species, the greater the R7cum, the greater the odds of a non-compliant result. The only exception was when R7cum

Fig. 3. Number of *Escherichia coli* (MPN/100 g) detected in bivalve molluscs collected from Sardinian production areas between 2018 and 2020. Red horizontal lines show the limit for an A area of (230 MPN 100/g) and an Area B (4,600 MPN 100/g). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Spearman’s rho coefficients between log MPN *Escherichia coli* 100/g and cumulative rainfall (mm)/number of rainy days between the day of sampling and up to 15 days before sampling.

Rainfall	Time	Mollusc species					Overall
		<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	<i>Ruditapes decussatus</i>	<i>Venus verrucosa</i>	<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	
Cumulative mm of rain	Day of sampling	0.195***	0.069 ^{NS}	0.191**	0.217*	0.001 ^{NS}	0.145***
	–1 day	0.201***	0.051 ^{NS}	0.123*	0.068 ^{NS}	0.066 ^{NS}	0.136***
	–3 days	0.247***	0.026 ^{NS}	0.199**	0.068 ^{NS}	0.162 ^{NS}	0.159***
	–5 days	0.298***	0.081 ^{NS}	0.262***	0.133 ^{NS}	0.153 ^{NS}	0.210***
	–7 days	0.328***	0.123**	0.245***	0.241*	0.222 ^{NS}	0.240***
N. Rainy days	–15 days	0.326***	0.049 ^{NS}	0.217***	0.193 ^{NS}	0.274 ^{NS}	0.217***
	Day of sampling	0.110**	0.043 ^{NS}	0.167***	0.259*	–0.028 ^{NS}	0.092***
	–1 day	0.168***	0.059 ^{NS}	0.091 ^{NS}	0.280**	–0.0955 ^{NS}	0.119***
	–3 days	0.216***	0.087 ^{NS}	0.211***	0.294**	–0.030 ^{NS}	0.169***
	–5 days	0.256***	0.084 ^{NS}	0.210***	0.169 ^{NS}	0.110 ^{NS}	0.185***
	–7 days	0.287***	0.074 ^{NS}	0.174***	0.117 ^{NS}	0.102 ^{NS}	0.188***
	–15 days	0.246***	–0.002 ^{NS}	0.180***	0.107 ^{NS}	0.0155 ^{NS}	0.153***

A rainy day was defined as day with a minimum level of precipitation of 1 mm. ^{NS}not significant; *0.01 ≤ P < 0.05; **0.001 ≤ P < 0.01; ***0.0001 ≤ P < 0.001.

was between 200 and 250 mm, which showed lower odds of non-compliance, as compared to 150–200 mm. Nonetheless, this result may have been affected by the small sample size within that category (Table 3). Although our results agree with most literature, some studies reported that the overall microbial load of bivalves in harvesting areas may improve after prolonged heavy rainfall events in some areas, suggesting a potential dilution effect (Lee & Morgan, 2003). It is important to note that, besides rainfall, there could be several other explanatory variables that influence *E. coli* contamination, such as the hydrogeology of the site of collection and catchment area, distance from the coast, seasonal variation, proximity to a pollution sources, water depth, tidal cycles, and several other factors including bivalve species and

wastewater treatment plants (Bougeard et al., 2011; Campos & Cachola, 2007; Campos et al., 2013; Campos et al., 2011; Ciccarelli et al., 2017; Colaiuda et al., 2021; Coulliette et al., 2009). The logistic regression model used in the present study accounted for the effects of season, county of origin, and bivalve species. The seasonal effect observed indicated that samples harvested in autumn had the greatest prevalence of non-compliance (32.1 %), which could be partially explained by the highest amount of cumulative rain recorded in this season (Table 3 and Supplementary Table 2). According to Regulation (EU) 2019/627 shellfish production areas are classified into three different quality levels (A-C) based on the level of *E. coli* in the flesh and intravalvular fluid. This sanitary measure is aimed to protect human health. Therefore, the

Fig. 4. Cumulative amount of rain (mm) at D0 (day of sampling) and 1, 3, 5, 7, and 15 days before sampling.

Table 3

Results of a multivariable logistic regression to estimate the odds of having *Escherichia coli* values above the limit for sanitary class A (>230 MPN/100 g), as a function of different cumulative rainfall categories in the 7 days before sampling (R7cum) and other covariates.

Explanatory variable	% non-compliance (N) ¹	OR ²	95 % CI ³	P-value
7-day cumulative rain (mm)				<0.0001
<10	15.32 (154/1005)	Referent		
10–50	20.13 (95/472)	1.47	1.09 1.99	
50–100	33.33 (65/195)	2.80	1.92 4.06	
100–150	41.89 (31/74)	3.79	2.23 6.43	
150–200	53.70 (29/54)	6.09	3.30 11.24	
200–250	29.41 (5/17)	3.42	1.09 10.76	
250–300	55.00 (11/20)	8.63	3.15 23.62	
>300	80.49 (33/41)	23.59	10.18 54.64	
Season				0.0025
Winter	12.44 (53/426)	Referent		
Autumn	32.12 (168/523)	2.03	1.40 2.93	
Spring	24.01 (121/504)	1.47	1.01 2.15	
Summer	18.63 (87/467)	1.47	0.99 2.17	
Species				0.1250
<i>Venus verrucosa</i>	20.21 (19/84)	Referent		
<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	30.43 (14/46)	1.46	0.58 3.68	
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	23.00 (115/500)	1.43	0.80 2.57	
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	20.42 (195/955)	1.37	0.76 2.46	
<i>Ruditapes decussatus</i>	26.46 (86/325)	2.04	1.08 3.85	
County				<0.0001
Carbonia-iglesias	4.11 (3/73)	Referent		
Cagliari	26.83 (117/436)	10.92	3.27 36.41	
Nuoro	39.29 (11/28)	16.50	3.94 69.00	
Ogliastra	7.84 (20/255)	2.18	0.61 7.80	
Olbia	25.75 (241/936)	10.89	3.28 36.15	
Oristano	19.78 (36/182)	9.10	2.60 31.88	
Sassari	10.00 (1/10)	3.14	0.27 36.29	

¹ % of samples with *E. coli* > 230 MPN/100 g.

² Adjusted odds ratio from a logistic regression multivariable model.

³ 95 % confidence interval.

microbiological quality of bivalve molluscs placed on the market can be affected by the quality of the area of origin and on the efficacy of post-harvesting treatment. Most Sardinian production areas are classified as category B, which requires that bivalve molluscs be subjected to a purification process before they can be marketed. The county of origin was significantly associated with the distribution of sanitary class; nonetheless, it has to be noted that the number of samples collected from each county varied considerably. Most of the samples were collected from Olbia (48.75 %), Cagliari (22.71 %), Ogliastra (13.28 %), and Oristano (9.48 %), whereas the other three counties cumulatively accounted for 5.78 % of the samples. The Carbonia-Iglesias (CI) county showed the lower prevalence of non-compliance to sanitary standards (4.11) and was used as reference. The highest values above the limit for sanitary class A were observed in Cagliari (CA), Olbia (OL) and Oristano (OR), with a prevalence of 26.8 % (O.R. 10.9), 25.8 % (O.R. 10.9) and 19.8 % (O.R. 9.1), respectively. Land use (e.g., agriculture and urbanization) can influence the relationship between precipitation (run-off) and water contamination (Lipp et al., 2001; Lunestad, Frantzen, Svanevik, Roiha, & Duinker, 2016; Stohlgren, Chase, Pielke, Kittel, & Baron, 1998). In fact, the different production areas of Sardinia have different degrees of anthropization and different economic activities that persist in the territory, which can represent possible sources of pollution in the water used to produce mussels. Regarding the possible sources of pollution from human activities where the molluscs farming facilities are located, there are peculiarities for each production area. The North-West area of Olbia (OL) traditionally has been one of the most productive areas for mussel cultivation, with several production sites. This area is strongly anthropized, with different industrial activities, including the presence of an important commercial and touristic harbour. During the summer period the population increases considerably, with increased discharge of polluted water that could exceed the wastewater treatment plant capacity. In the South, mollusc farming in Cagliari (CA) is mostly located in a very populated area (Santa Gilla), with different productive activities, suggesting that contamination is mainly of anthropic origin. On the West coast, the Oristano area (OR), with a long tradition of shellfish farming, is characterized by a thriving livestock farming sector, with a potential impact of animal manure and sewage sludge as contamination sources.

The present study, despite the limitation in the number of variable studies, provides a practical approach to predict the odds of *E. coli* contamination in bivalve flesh after rainfall events. In fact, cost and time-consuming investigation should be conducted to obtain data necessary to account for the several factors that potentially impact on contamination. The objective of the present study was to provide overall information on the impact of rainfall on the concentration of *E. coli* in

bivalve molluscs reared in Sardinia based on the available and accessible rainfall data. The findings of the present study can be extrapolated to the specific areas of Sardinia, and ad hoc studies should be conducted on bivalve molluscs reared in other geographical locations.

5. Conclusions

According to European shellfish Control Regulations when *E. coli* monitoring shows results above the threshold, the sites should be closed to prevent bivalves from reaching the market. However, among European countries differences exist on approaches in handling *E. coli* results above the threshold. In Italy resuming harvesting is allowed if a repeated sample taken within one week does not exceed the classification threshold. The timeframe used to resample for reopening after a rainfall event is critical. The results of the present study demonstrate that the greatest association between rainfall and the increase in *E. coli* concentration occurs 7 days after the rainfall event. The odds of having an *E. coli* concentration above the threshold for class A depends on the mm of cumulative rain in the 7 days lag-time period. The higher R7cum, the higher the odds of anomalous results. The R7cum > 300 mm increased by 23 times the odds of non-compliant results, as compared to R7cum < 10 mm. On a practical basis, operator should be aware before harvesting of the increased probability of contamination in the week following heavy rain. Results of the present study could assist food business operator to better make harvesting decisions, and official control authorities to interpret anomalous results after rainfall.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A.G. Mudadu: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **C. Spanu:** Data curation, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **S. Salza:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **G. Piras:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **M.T. Uda:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **L. Giagnoni:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **G. Fois:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **J.G. Pereira:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **J.C.F. Pantoja:** Formal analysis, Software, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **S. Virgilio:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **T. Tedde:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2023.113563>.

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